

THE LEVEL OF AWARENESS ON TELEHEALTH AVAILABILITY AMONG PREGNANT CLIENTS OF BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA

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ABSTRACT

Telehealth has emerged as a transformative approach in healthcare delivery and is gradually being adopted in the Philippines. Despite its growing relevance, there is a lack of studies assessing awareness of existing telehealth services in Nueva Vizcaya. This study aimed to evaluate the level of awareness of pregnant clients regarding telehealth availability in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya—a vulnerable population with a constant need for maternal care—and to determine the correlation between their awareness levels and demographic profiles, including age, location, educational attainment, and income. A quantitative, descriptive-correlational research design was employed, involving 139 pregnant clients aged 10–49 in their first or second trimester, selected through stratified random sampling across 25 barangays. Data were collected face-to-face from September 2024 to January 2025 using a structured and reliable questionnaire (Cronbach's $\alpha \geq 0.91$), adapted from Z & S (2018) and Department of Health (2022). Results showed moderate awareness in general knowledge (Mean = 2.78), provider (Mean = 2.64), and requirements (Mean = 2.85), but lower awareness in scheduling (Mean = 2.33) and contact platforms (Mean = 2.37). Significant correlations were found between awareness and both age ($\rho = 0.185$, $p = 0.029$) and educational attainment ($\rho = 0.172$, $p = 0.043$), while no substantial relationship was observed with location or income. The findings underscore the need for enhanced information dissemination through community-based education and digital outreach. An Information, Education, and Communication (IEC) material was developed to support awareness initiatives and strengthen institutional collaboration, ultimately aiming to improve maternal healthcare access and telehealth utilization.

Keywords: *Awareness, Pregnant Clients, Telehealth*

INTRODUCTION

Telehealth usage surged by 50% in 2020 due to its convenience and efficiency, especially for remote areas (Bestsenny et al., 2021; Powell et al., 2017). It showed high satisfaction among patients, including pregnant women (Fleischhacker, 2020; Haleem et al., 2021; Atkinson et al., 2023). While globally adopted, awareness remains low—even in countries like the U.S., Singapore, and the Philippines (Power, 2019; Praveen, 2020; Hossain et al., 2019; Dalisay et al., 2022). In Bayombong, the Region II Trauma and Medical Center offers telehealth services, but no study has yet assessed pregnant clients' awareness of its availability—prompting this research.

Asian countries like Thailand and Singapore have integrated telehealth into healthcare (Viriyataveekul, 2020; Ministry of Health, 2023), though awareness remains low (Hossain et al., 2019). In the Philippines, it gained popularity during the pandemic (Bashshur et al., 2016), with DOH, PhilHealth, and NGOs offering services (Cordero, 2023). Awareness influences usage and outcomes (Greenhalgh et al., 2020; Snoswell et al., 2020; Kruse et al., 2017; Haleem et al., 2021). Despite House Bill No. 7422, many remain unaware (Dalisay et al., 2022). In Nueva Vizcaya, RIITMC offers teleconsults, requiring patient awareness and readiness (Gali, 2022; Isotoma Team, 2019; Muzamwese, 2019).

Telehealth caters to those who live far away, benefitting pregnant clients who lived remotely (Gao et al., 2022). In the UK, telehealth was rated as good or very good (Quinn et al., 2020), and women expressed satisfaction with virtual prenatal visits (Liu et al., 2021; Peahl et al., 2021). It helps reduce financial burdens through lower payment costs (Cuellar, 2022) and supports interventions like smoking cessation, breastfeeding, and weight management during pregnancy (Shmerling et al., 2022). It also supplements mental health care (Cantor et al., 2022) and offers education and counseling through follow-ups (Özkan and Yaman, 2021; Weigel et al., 2020; DeNicola et al., 2020; Kusyanti et al., 2022). It helps manage stress and avoids exposure to nosocomial infections (Pilosof et al., 2021; Farrell et al., 2022). Given the vulnerability of pregnancy (Abu-Raya et al., 2020; News-Medical.net, 2022), telehealth promotes continuity of care and positive outcomes (Kusyanti et al., 2022), supports prenatal compliance, and reduces maternal mortality (Jeganathan et al., 2020; Bridging the Gaps with Telehealth, 2023). Bruno et al. (2023) emphasized its convenience and medical reliability, but Atkinson et al. (2023) noted it should supplement, not replace, physical exams. Telehealth remains underdeveloped (Macariola et al., 2021), requiring government efforts for awareness and provider training. Improving services and overcoming barriers can enhance consumer awareness (West, 2019).

Telehealth can expand access to treatment for marginalized communities with geographical and transportation challenges, improving healthcare by providing patients in rural areas access to medical providers at more comprehensive facilities than Health Stations enhancing health outcomes, and addressing issues like physician shortages and transportation time (World Health Organization, 2010; Batsis et al., 2019; Anderson & Singh, 2021). Age, income, educational attainment, and geographic location are all crucial characteristics that might influence healthtech literacy. By addressing these factors, people can better understand how to use healthtech tools, which can lead to improved health and well-being (View of Factors Influencing Healthtech Literacy: An Empirical Analysis of Socioeconomic, Demographic, Technological, and Health-Related Variables, 2018).

The literature highlights the development and positive impact of telehealth, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic. It serves as a valuable supplement to in-person visits, offering accessible and flexible healthcare, particularly for vulnerable groups like pregnant clients. Despite its benefits, many remain unaware of telehealth due to poor communication. Awareness is influenced by factors such as age, location, educational attainment, and income level. Therefore, this study is significant as it aims to determine the level of awareness of pregnant clients regarding telehealth availability in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya.

Statement of the Problem

The study aimed to determine the level of awareness of telehealth availability of 139 pregnant clients from Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. This study was completed by March 2025. It aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Location;
 - 1.3 Educational Attainment; and
 - 1.4 Income Level?

2. What is the level of awareness of pregnant clients on telehealth availability in the municipality of

Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya in the following areas:

- 2.1 General Knowledge;
- 2.2 Provider;
- 2.3 Schedule;
- 2.4 Contact Medium/ Platform; and
- 2.5 Requirements?

3. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' level of awareness on telehealth availability and their demographic profile in terms of:

- 3.1 Age;
- 3.2 Location;
- 3.3 Educational Attainment; and
- 3.4 Income Level?

4. What IEC (Information, Education, and Communication) material may be developed based on the results of the study?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative descriptive-correlational design. It involved description of the demographic characteristics of the pregnant clients, their level of awareness on general telehealth knowledge and on telehealth availability in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya—provider, schedule, platforms available, and requirements. The study also examined the relationship between the respondents' demographic profile and their level of awareness.

The research was conducted in Bayombong, of Nueva Vizcaya. Central barangays—Bonfal East, Bonfal Proper, Bonfal West, La Torre North, Magsaysay, Don Domingo Maddela, Don Tomas Maddela, Don Mariano Marcos, District IV, Don Mariano Perez, La Torre South, Salvacion, San Nicolas, Santa Rosa, and Vista Alegre. Remote barangays—Casat, Paitan, Ipil Cuneg, Luyang, Banging, Busilac, Cabuaan, Magapuy, Buenavista, and Masoc. Telehealth is available at Region II Trauma and Medical Center, a tertiary hospital in the municipality. However, no assessment had been made of local residents' awareness of this telehealth service, providing an ideal environment for gauging pregnant clients' awareness of telehealth availability.

The 139 sample size, derived from the population size of 216 based on the MHO's data, was determined via OpenEpi with a confidence level of ninety-five percent (95%) and a five percent (5%) margin of error. The respondents were selected through stratified random sampling. The population was divided into twenty-five (25) subgroups. The respondents included pregnant clients of Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, aged ten to forty-nine (10-49) years, and in their first and second trimesters of pregnancy. Pregnant women in their third trimester of pregnancy, cognitively impaired, beyond the limit of the age range of the MHO data, nonresidents of the Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, non-gadget users, illiterate and digitally illiterate, and nonconsensual respondents were excluded.

A structured questionnaire was developed with three sections. Section I collected demographic information—name, age, location, educational attainment, and income level. Section II measured the awareness on general telehealth knowledge adapted from the study of Jawaharlal Institute of Postgraduate Medical Education & Research (2018), wherein a four-point Likert scale was employed (1=Not Aware, 2=Slightly Aware, 3=Moderately Aware, 4=Extremely Aware).

Section III also used the four-point likert scale to measure the awareness in the existing telehealth in Nueva Vizcaya—provider, schedule, contact medium/platform, and requirements based on DOH's data (DOH, 2022). The questionnaire was translated into Filipino by Ms. Precious B. Resurreccion, LPT. The reliability of the instrument was also checked using Cronbach's alpha (≥ 0.91).

Prior to data collection, an ethical approval was given by Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The frequency-percentage distribution was used to describe the demographic profile of the respondents, and the mean range was used to analyze the level of awareness regarding telehealth availability on a 4-point Likert scale. The following ranges: 3.50–4.00 = *Extremely Aware*, 2.50–3.49 = *Moderately Aware*, 1.50–2.49 = *Slightly Aware*, and 1.00–1.49 = *Not Aware*. Particularly, Spearman's Rho determined the between the respondents' demographic profile and their level of awareness on telehealth availability.

The researchers addressed ethical considerations by acknowledging a potential conflict of interest due to their affiliation with the Region II Trauma and Medical Center and mitigating bias by excluding themselves from data analysis related to telehealth services. Participant confidentiality and data protection were ensured through informed consent, data anonymization, encryption, and controlled access, complying with the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Vulnerable participants aged 10–17 were provided with age-appropriate assent and consent procedures involving parents or guardians, with clear communication about study purpose, risks, benefits, and rights, avoiding coercion. Risks such as confidentiality breaches and participant distress were minimized through secure data handling and flexible scheduling, while benefits included enhanced telehealth awareness and improved healthcare access. The research, conducted to fulfill academic requirements at Saint Mary's University without external funding, credits student researchers and faculty advisors, and plans to disseminate findings via social media, community forums, and academic presentations to promote telehealth services for pregnant women in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

SECTION 1: PROFILE OF THE RESPONDENTS

The majority of respondents were aged 20–49 (82.7%), with most living in center barangays (64%). Educationally, most had completed high school (33.8%) or were high school undergraduates (24.5%). In terms of income, 46.8% reported having just enough, while 34.5% had inadequate income. Overall, most respondents were younger adults from central areas with secondary education and sufficient income.

SECTION 2: PRESENTATION OF THE RESPONDENTS' LEVEL OF AWARENESS ON TELEHEALTH AVAILABILITY IN TERMS OF GENERAL KNOWLEDGE, PROVIDER, SCHEDULE, CONTACT MEDIUM/PLATFORM, AND REQUIREMENTS

Table 4 shows that pregnant clients are moderately aware of telehealth availability, with a mean score of 2.78, indicating reasonable general knowledge. This supports findings by Hamed et al. (2022) and Kabir et al. (2024), but contrasts with studies by Power (2019), Hossain et al. (2019), and Dalisay et al. (2022), which found limited awareness in vulnerable groups. The gap remains a barrier to telehealth use (Praveen, 2020; Malhotra et al., 2020), highlighting the need for awareness campaigns and government efforts (Ezinne et al., 2023; Bekyieriya et al., 2023).

Table 4. *The Mean Level of Awareness of Pregnant Clients on Telehealth Availability in Terms of Their General Knowledge*

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Qualitative Description
General Knowledge	2.78	0.82	Moderately Aware
Statements for General Knowledge Section			
1. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) can be used effectively in health services.	2.87	0.96	Moderately Aware
2. Telemedicine is a branch of telehealth.	2.65	0.99	Moderately Aware
3. Face-to-face interaction between patients and doctors is possible through telehealth.	2.75	0.94	Moderately Aware
4. Telehealth can deliver services in remote areas.	2.70	1.04	Moderately Aware
5. You can send a picture to the doctors for consultation.	2.54	1.05	Moderately Aware
6. Laboratory results such as ECG and X-ray can now be sent to doctors to ask for a professional opinion.	2.76	1.09	Moderately Aware
7. Telehealth can be used in the event of disasters such as pandemic, especially in affected and inaccessible areas.	2.90	0.99	Moderately Aware
8. Telehealth is the use of telecommunications to provide medical information and services.	2.96	0.97	Moderately Aware
9. Patient consultation on proper medication intake can be done through telehealth.	2.91	1.01	Moderately Aware
10. Through telehealth, patients can consult professionals through the internet.	2.80	0.92	Moderately Aware
11. Examination of patients can be communicated through telehealth.	2.81	0.98	Moderately Aware
12. Electronic medical records of patients can be maintained through telehealth.	2.74	0.98	Moderately Aware
13. Follow-ups with patients can be done through telehealth.	2.81	1.02	Moderately Aware
14. Healthcare via the internet is a recognized service.	2.79	0.98	Moderately Aware

Table 5 indicates that pregnant clients in Nueva Vizcaya were moderately aware (mean = 2.64) of telehealth services, especially those by R2TMC, showing some familiarity but limited in-depth knowledge. This limited awareness may restrict full utilization. Supporting studies link awareness to use: Greenhalgh et al. (2020) connected awareness with usage, Parameshwarappa & Olickal (2023) cited low eSanjeevani OPD use in India due to limited awareness, and Al-Rayes et al. (2021) reported increased awareness raised adoption of Saudi's 937 services.

Table 5. *The Mean Level of Awareness of Pregnant Clients on the Existing Telehealth in Nueva Vizcaya in Terms of the Provider*

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Qualitative Description
Provider Mean	2.64	1.19	Moderately Aware
Statements for Provider Section			
1. R2TMC provides a telehealth service called "OPD Teleconsult Clinic."	2.63	1.24	Moderately Aware
2. R2TMC's OPD Teleconsult Clinic is a free health service.	2.65	1.24	Moderately Aware
3. R2TMC's OPD Teleconsult Clinic is a way to seek medical advice from professional doctors.	2.66	1.22	Moderately Aware
4. The OPD Teleconsult Clinic includes consultation for pregnant women because OB-GYNE service is included.	2.63	1.23	Moderately Aware
5. Pregnant women can use the OPD Teleconsult Clinic for prenatal consultations.	2.61	1.25	Moderately Aware

The table indicates that pregnant clients in Nueva Vizcaya possess only a slight awareness of the telehealth services available, particularly regarding scheduling (Mean = 2.33, SD = 1.20). This suggests a need for improved communication strategies to better inform this population about the availability and scheduling of telehealth options. Enhancing awareness is crucial to ensuring pregnant clients can access and utilize these services effectively.

Table 6. *The Mean Level of Awareness of Pregnant Clients on the Existing Telehealth in Nueva Vizcaya in Terms of the Schedule*

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Qualitative Description
Schedule Mean	2.33	1.20	Slightly Aware
Statements for the Schedule Section			
1. R2TMC's OB-GYNE OPD Teleconsult schedule is every Thursday, 1:00 pm-4:00 pm.	2.24	1.24	Slightly Aware
2. It is necessary to make an appointment before consulting on the stated schedule.	2.42	1.28	Slightly Aware

The table presents that pregnant clients in Nueva Vizcaya have limited awareness "slightly aware," (Mean = 2.37, SD = 1.24), regarding the contact medium or platform for telehealth services. This suggests that while they possess some knowledge, they need further clarity on who to contact or which platform to utilize for scheduling or accessing services. Improving this understanding is essential for facilitating telehealth adoption among this population.

Table 7. *The Mean Level of Awareness of Pregnant Clients on the Existing Telehealth in Nueva Vizcaya in Terms of the Contact Medium/Platform*

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Qualitative Description
Contact Medium/ Platform Mean	2.37	1.24	Slightly Aware
Statements for the Contact Medium/ Platform Section			
1. To schedule an appointment at the OB-GYNE OPD Teleconsult of R2TMC, you can contact the nursing attendant, Danley Cabiles, through the hotline number 09673360046.	2.34	1.28	Slightly Aware
2. You can also message their Facebook page "Riitmc Opd Teleconsult" to schedule an appointment and questions about this service.	2.41	1.28	Slightly Aware

Table 8 highlights the mean level of awareness among pregnant clients regarding the requirements needed to access telehealth services in Nueva Vizcaya. The findings indicate that their overall awareness is classified as "moderately aware" (Mean = 2.85, SD = 1.19).

Table 8. *The Mean Level of Awareness of Pregnant Clients on the Existing Telehealth in Nueva Vizcaya in Terms of the Requirements*

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Qualitative Description
Requirements Mean	2.85	1.19	Moderately Aware
Statements for the Requirements Section			
1. A mobile phone/computer/laptop/internet connection is required for effective teleconsultation.	2.83	1.22	Moderately Aware
2. It is also necessary to provide information about oneself, especially the condition and health information.	2.87	1.22	Moderately Aware

The results reflected that most of the respondents exhibited moderate awareness in terms of their general knowledge about telehealth, the provider, and the requirements needed to utilize this service. However, respondents have limited awareness of the schedule and contact medium/platform associated with the telehealth in Region II Trauma and Medical Center.

Table 9. *Overall Mean Level of Awareness for Each Section*

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Qualitative Description
General Knowledge Mean	2.78	0.82	Moderately Aware
Provider Mean	2.64	1.19	Moderately Aware
Schedule Mean	2.33	1.20	Slightly Aware
Contact Medium/ Platform Mean	2.37	1.24	Slightly Aware
Requirements Mean	2.85	1.19	Moderately Aware

SECTION 3: PRESENTATION ON THE CORRELATION BETWEEN THE RESPONDENTS' LEVEL OF AWARENESS ON TELEHEALTH AVAILABILITY AND THEIR DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE

Table 10. Analysis of Significant Relationship through Correlation Coefficients and p-Values across Respondents' Level of Awareness on Telehealth Availability and Their Various Demographic Profile

		Age	Location	Highest Educational Attainment	Income Level
General Knowledge	Correlation Coefficient	.185*	-0.089	.172*	0.091
	p-value	0.029	0.300	0.043	0.288
Provider	Correlation Coefficient	.174*	0.116	0.016	0.073
	p-value	0.041	0.174	0.850	0.394
Schedule	Correlation Coefficient	0.060	0.141	-0.040	-0.022
	p-value	0.481	0.099	0.640	0.796
Contact Medium/ Platform	Correlation Coefficient	0.135	0.114	-0.018	0.044
	p-value	0.114	0.182	0.838	0.608
Requirements	Correlation Coefficient	0.051	0.037	0.045	0.105
	p-value	0.552	0.663	0.601	0.221

A positive relationship was found between age and general knowledge, suggesting higher awareness among older adults. This aligns with the importance of technology for older adults during health crises (Von Humboldt et al., 2020). Similarly, age correlated positively with knowledge of the telehealth provider indicating that older individuals were more informed about the local telehealth provider, contrasting the findings that younger individuals were aware of telehealth more (Miyawaki et al., 2021). A positive correlation was also found between the highest level of education achieved and general knowledge of telehealth services. This is supported by Tariq et al. (2023), who concluded that individuals with post-secondary education had a higher likelihood of understanding telehealth. Al-Shobry et al. (2024) also added that educated individuals' have greater awareness and usage of technology-based services. Umayam et al. (2022) also shared that educational attainment is a major contributing factor with internet skills (Umayam et al., 2022). No significant correlations were established between general knowledge and the income level, and between income level and telehealth awareness.

SECTION 4: INFORMATION, EDUCATION, AND COMMUNICATION (IEC) MATERIAL

The IEC material derived based on the findings is an informative tarpaulin, which can be posted in every barangay health station in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. It consists of: general knowledge about telehealth and its benefits, the primary provider of telehealth in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya along with its requirements, especially in the scheduling of the said service, and the platforms that can be used to access telehealth. The respondents had moderate levels of awareness in the areas of general knowledge on telehealth, the provider present in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, and the requirements needed to access it. Hence, supplementary information is needed in these areas to enable the respondents to be fully aware of its details. Substantially, the tarpaulin emphasized the schedule of consultations for OB-GYNE clients and the contact mediums available since the respondents exhibited low levels of awareness in these areas.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

This study established that the respondents' level of awareness on telehealth was characterized as moderately aware in terms of general knowledge about telehealth, the provider available (R2TMC), and the needed requirements to access telehealth. These indicate that respondents displayed some familiarity with the concept of using telecommunication technologies for health services, recognizing its potential benefits, including accessibility in remote areas and the ability to consult without physical visits. However, significant gaps remained in the schedule and platform/contact medium awareness.

A notable correlation was found between age and educational attainment with awareness levels. Older respondents and those with higher educational qualifications demonstrated a greater understanding of telehealth services. These insights emphasize the importance of targeting educational efforts toward younger and less formally educated pregnant women. Overall, the results emphasized the need for improved information dissemination through collaborating with the institution, community-based educational campaigns and digital outreach among pregnant clients. Strengthening awareness initiatives can help optimize telehealth utilization, improving maternal healthcare access and outcomes.

Recommendations

1. Educational forum for supplementation of the general knowledge about telehealth, and enhancement of the awareness of pregnant clients regarding the detailed information of the existing telehealth in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya.
2. A pamphlet containing necessary information about the existing telehealth with simple and easy-to-understand details for pregnant clients.
3. Dissemination to healthcare workers on significant details about the existing telehealth in the municipality to ensure that pregnant clients are informed about their options.
4. Future research can evaluate the barriers faced by pregnant clients, particularly younger and less formally educated.
5. Collaboration with the municipal mayor to share the study's findings, enabling them to facilitate the dissemination of vital information about available telehealth services, ultimately enhancing the comfort and experience of pregnant clients during their prenatal consultations.

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